

ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON PSYCHOSOCIAL WELL-BEING AND ADJUSTMENT TOWARD FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 6

Pages: 718-724

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2093

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12813423

Manuscript Accepted: 05-072024

Attitude of Secondary School Students on Psychosocial Well-being and Adjustment toward Face-To-Face Classes

John Noel E. Fermin,* May Caroline C. Gajes, Alyssa Dianne Paulette F. Guda, Gracious Bai B. Cariaga, Felisa R. Andres, Dianne M. David

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has formed significant disruptions in the education system, prompting profound changes in students' psychosocial well-being and adjustment to face-to-face classes. This study aimed to assess the psychosocial well-being and adjustment levels of secondary school students transitioning to in-person classes and to design a school-based mental health program. This present study employed a quantitative, descriptive research design using the *Pagsusuri sa Sikososyal para sa Balik Eskwela* (PSBE), an adopted questionnaire from the Department of Education's Psychosocial Activity Pack, to gather data from 375 secondary school students, 212 were junior high school students, and 163 were senior high school students. Further, 197 were females, and 178 were males. Notable findings indicated that students generally exhibited strong psychosocial well-being skills upon returning to face-to-face classes, with an overall rating of 3.75. In contrast, their psychosocial adjustment to the return of in-person classes was rated at 3.96, denoting high interest. However, learners expressed concerns regarding their ability to articulate thoughts and feelings and demonstrate strengths and abilities in school activities. These results carry implications for guidance and counseling services, implementing a mental health awareness program, integrating the Psychosocial Support Activity Pack in the Homeroom Guidance, and future research in this field.

Keywords: *psychosocial well-being, psychosocial adjustment, secondary school students, mental health awareness*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted the education system worldwide, significantly changing how students learn and interact with their peers and teachers. While this shift has brought about new opportunities, it has also presented challenges, especially for their psychosocial well-being and adjustments, with many experiencing heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. As we look towards a post-pandemic world, students' psychosocial well-being and adjustment need to be assessed to determine and develop effective strategies that will enhance students' psychosocial well-being, leading to academic success and overall development.

Psychological and social concerns among students were already seen as a significant challenge before the COVID-19 pandemic (Nsereko et al., 2014). During high school, students undergo a significant transition in their lives, characterized by physical, social, and emotional changes, affecting their psychosocial well-being and adjustment.

Psychosocial well-being is a subjective construct that includes psychological and social aspects of an individual, which influence their overall functionality in achieving their true potential as members of society (Larson, 1996; Martikainen, 2002; and Kumar, 2020). On the other hand, psychosocial adjustment pertains to an individual's ability to adjust to their surroundings, indicating that they possess the necessary mechanisms to feel well, integrate, meet environmental needs, and accomplish their goals (Madariaga et al., 2014).

Since the transition to blended learning, the psychosocial well-being of students has become a significant focus within education and psychology research. The abrupt shift from face-to-face classes to online learning and other modalities has profoundly impacted students' psychological, physical, and emotional well-being. The traditional classroom environment, where students could develop their skills through regular direct interaction with peers, has been disrupted by this pandemic, leading to isolation and compromised overall development.

Loades et al. (2020) assert that lockdowns, remote learning, and restrictions on social gatherings have resulted in social isolation for many students. Lack of social interaction with peers and teachers can lead to feelings of loneliness and depression. Similarly, the pandemic has also been associated with a rise in mental health issues among students. A study conducted by Aristovnik et al. (2020) indicates an increase in the prevalence of depression and anxiety symptoms among learners during a pandemic, which can have a lasting impact on their psychosocial well-being if distance learning continues to be practiced in the educational setting.

The psychosocial well-being of students is crucial in their overall development and success, and it relies heavily on factors like emotional safety, family support, and peer relationships (Brenner & Letich, 2023). Emotional safety, defined as feeling accepted and embraced for one's true self, is essential for healthy relationships (Brenner & Letich, 2023) and contributes to learners' total well-being. Studies indicate that strong family support systems and positive peer interactions contribute to better psychosocial well-being among students (Kessler et al., 2020; Smith & Jones, 2019). Social and emotional learning (SEL) programs have significantly improved students' social and emotional skills, attitudes, behavior, and academic performance (Durlak et al., 2011), emphasizing the importance of emotional safety and learning.

Further, studies have found that self-awareness, self-expression, self-regulation, problem-solving skills, self-confidence, and empathy

are vital components of psychosocial well-being. Psychologists Shelley Duval and Robert Wicklund, as cited in the work of Betz (2022), assert that highly self-aware learners, either in private or in public, have a high level of psychosocial well-being. In the same way, Barowski and Orr (2021) emphasized that when a person is given an opportunity to outwardly represent his or her thoughts, feelings, and interests, it can make him or her more psychosocially well.

On the one hand, when learners have good social and mental health, they tend to be able to regulate themselves, including their emotions, behaviors, and reactions to the things happening around them, either good or bad (Raising Children, 2021). Additionally, a learner who can function better at home and in school, deal with the everyday stresses of life, and approach things under their control or settle things independently has a high chance of having good psychosocial well-being (Llego, 2022).

Besides, Uludag and Oney (2013) discovered that a learner who knows his/her strengths and weaknesses well has a positive view of oneself, sets realistic expectations and goals, communicates assertively, can handle criticism, and has high psychosocial well-being. Finally, empathy has also been considered in the study of Goleman (2005) as a necessary characteristic in building connections and healthy relationships, as it helps the person to understand and react to others' emotions and needs.

Hence, understanding the factors that contribute to the psychosocial well-being of learners is crucial in developing effective mental health awareness programs to promote their overall development and academic success. Several interventions have been proposed and studied to enhance the psychosocial well-being of secondary school students. One practical approach is implementing school-based counseling services (Green et al., 2021). Providing students with access to trained counselors within the school setting can offer a safe space to discuss their concerns and receive guidance on managing psychosocial challenges.

Another promising intervention is the promotion of mindfulness and stress management techniques in schools (Harrison & Adams, 2020). Moreover, schools can also provide support systems, such as counseling services and mental health resources, to promote students' mental health and well-being. Finally, schools can provide opportunities for students to engage in extracurricular activities, promoting their social development and emotional well-being. Hence, this study sought to determine the level of psychosocial well-being and the psychosocial adjustment to the in-person classes of high school students.

This study holds significance for various individuals and organizations. The School Administration, facilitated by the Human Development Center, will benefit by gaining insights into students' psychosocial well-being, allowing them to design a School-based Mental Health Awareness Program to address students' needs in in-person classes better. Teachers will become more aware of students' psychosocial status, leading to a more supportive emotional climate in school and enabling them to meet diverse learning needs. Students will gain an understanding of their own well-being, access resources for improved mental health, and healthier adjustment from distance learning to face-to-face initiatives. Parents will gain insight into their child's challenges, enabling support and collaboration with schools for effective guidance in their children's transition. Other school stakeholders will recognize the importance of prioritizing one's mental health, leading to collaborative efforts and resource allocation for community initiatives supporting psychosocial well-being improvement. Additionally, future researchers will benefit from this study as it will further explore related topics, offering new observations and interventions for addressing challenges in transitioning to the "new normal."

Literature Review

Psychosocial wellbeing

Psychosocial well-being, as defined by Dodge and colleagues (2012), is an equilibrium between an individual's psychological resources and life challenges. This is influenced by factors such as emotional stability, social relationships, and a sense of purpose, while Huppert (2009) defines psychosocial wellbeing as the combination of feeling good and functioning effectively.

In other context, the concept refers to a wide range of issues, including, but not limited to, mental, emotional, social, physical, economic, cultural, and spiritual health. It is agreed that a model of psychosocial well-being should include and reflect the interconnectedness of the various aspects of overall well-being (Keyes, 2002; Linley et al., 2009). From this concept, the WHO (2022) describes psychosocial wellbeing as an interplay between psychological factors and the social environment.

On the other hand, Ryff and Singer (1996) provides another concept that psychosocial wellbeing is comprised of six dimensions: self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and personal growth. In addition, Seligman's PERMA model identifies five essential elements of wellbeing: Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment (Seligman, 2011). This model underscores that wellbeing involves not just the absence of negative emotions, but the presence of positive elements that contribute to a fulfilling life. Considering the above concepts, psychosocial wellbeing truly represents a holistic view of an individual's functioning and resilience in the face of life challenges.

Therefore, psychosocial wellbeing is a concept that encompasses emotional, social, and psychological dimensions of an individual's life.

Psychosocial adjustment

Compas and colleagues (1988) define psychosocial adjustment as the dynamic process of managing emotional, cognitive, and

behavioral responses to stressors and changes in life. Therefore, an effective coping strategy that result in stable mental health and social functioning are necessary for effective adjustment.

Moreover, Harter (1990) describes psychosocial adjustment as the degree to which an individual feels competent and has a positive self-concept within their social environment. It involves achieving personal goals, maintaining positive relationships, and experiencing emotional well-being.

In a more recent article, the Springer Publishing (n.d.) mentioned that psychosocial adjustment involves coping with the psychological and social challenges posed by the condition. It requires adapting to the limitations and lifestyle changes brought about by the illness while maintaining mental health and social relationships. A recent study by Doucette (2023) highlighted that psychosocial adjustment is significantly influenced by personal and clinical factors such as age, educational background, and preoperative education.

Hence, psychosocial adjustment is a process that helps people find a balance between their internal psychological and social concerns as they adjust to changes and pressures in their life.

Students' Psychosocial wellbeing

Research conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic by Dodd et al. (2021) revealed that the crisis significantly affected students' wellbeing. It was found that approximately 66.3% of students reported low to very low levels of wellbeing, with higher levels of anxiety and stress due to the pandemic.

In addition, recent studies found that online learning presents various challenges, with many students experiencing lost learning opportunities, leading to psychological distress and low level of wellbeing (Baik et al., 2019; & Shackle, 2019).

Sutomo and colleagues (2022) indicated in their study that there is a rise in psychological stress, anxiety, and depression among high school students during the period of online learning. The isolation, lack of in-person social interactions, and the constant screen time contributed significantly to these adverse effects.

Local studies have found that the sudden change to online learning put learners under a great deal of stress and anxiety due to their inability to stay motivated and engaged, students' anxiety and sadness levels increased (Serrano, 2023; Carreon & Manansala, 2021). Further, Lim and colleagues (2022) discovered that the lack of face-to-face interaction made it difficult for students to express themselves and seek help, which in turn affected their self-confidence and overall psychosocial wellbeing. Finally, research by Azmi and Azmi (2022) showed that students in high school participated less in academic activities and felt less confident in their academic skills, which contributed to a further decline in their self-expression and self-esteem.

Students' Psychosocial adjustment

Numerous children showed resilience and adaptability in spite of the challenges brought by distance learning. Research revealed that students exhibited a general sense of optimism and were able to overcome the challenges posed by remote education (Buško & Bezinović, 2021).

However, many students had a difficulty adjusting during the pandemic due to lack of a structured environment, technological issues, and the absence of in-person interactions with peers and teachers (Carreon & Manansala, 2021).

Hence, according to a study by Martin et al. (2021), a student's ability to adapt is critical to their psychosocial adjustment when learning remotely. To cope with distance learning, adaptability entails modifying one's actions, thoughts, and feelings.

School's Mental Health Program

Chaudhry et al. (2024) indicates that both formal and informal support systems significantly influence students' psychological well-being. Institutional support, including policies and practices that create a safe and positive environment, along with support from family and friends, helps students feel a sense of belonging and cope better with academic and personal challenges. These support systems can reduce incidences of mental illness and promote overall well-being.

Further, Psychosocial support activities were introduced by the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) to assist students in managing the difficulties associated with learning remotely, and to foster their resilience and general well-being throughout the epidemic. Peer support groups, mental health awareness seminars, and virtual counselling were some of these initiatives (Llego, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers used a quantitative approach, particularly a descriptive research design, to describe secondary school students' attitudes regarding psychosocial well-being and adjustment toward the return of face-to-face classes. This design involves collecting quantitative information to describe or identify the characteristics of an observed phenomenon (McCombes, 2023).

Participants

This study was conducted at the University of La Salette, Incorporated-High School in the City of Santiago, Philippines. From the population of 2,383 high school students, a sample of three hundred seventy-five (375) were chosen to serve as participants of the study using Raosoft online sample size calculator. Of the 375 participants, 212 were junior high school students, and 163 were senior high school students. Further, 197 were females, and 178 were males. Most of the participants were female and junior high school students. Participants were selected through a simple random sampling method. In this sampling method, each population member has an equal chance of being selected, and the method does not need much information about the whole population (Thomas, 2023). These students were chosen as participants, assuming an appropriate mental health program in the institution would be made after the study.

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a survey questionnaire with two parts. The first part focused on the participants' background; the second part was the *Pagsusuri sa Sikososyal para sa Balik Eskwela* (PSBE), an adopted questionnaire from the Department of Education's Psychosocial Activity Pack. The PSBE is a 13-item instrument. The first eight items on the questionnaire correspond to the key psychosocial well-being skills, namely emotional safety, self-awareness, self-expression, self-regulation, problem-solving (help-seeking), problem-solving (self-reliance), self-confidence, and empathy. The remaining five items cover the different aspects of learners' psychosocial adjustment to the in-person learning modality, which includes affect, motivation, perception of face-to-face modality vis-à-vis academic learning, perceived physical safety, and self-agency towards physical safety (Llego, 2022).

Procedure

The researchers sought permission from the school administration before administering the questionnaire. The schedule was set according to the participants' availability at the institution's Psychological Testing Unit during the start of the face-to-face learning modality. Before the participants answered the questions, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and what the questions were about, and written informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to the study. This was to avoid any misunderstanding of any item and discuss possible risks associated with the study.

Data Analysis

The data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted using PSPP, a statistical analysis tool developed to be free and open-source. The respondents' attitudes on psychosocial well-being and adjustment towards face-to-face modality were scored and interpreted using the PSBE scale guide (as seen in Table 1). Then, the mean scores of the respondents were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Table 1. *Arbitrary Scale*

Scale	Adjectival Description	
4.20-5.00	Lubos na Sumasang-ayon (Strongly Agree)	Very high
3.40-4.19	Sumasang-ayon (Agree)	High
2.60-3.39	Walang kinikilingan (Neutral)	Moderate
1.80-2.59	Hindi sumasang-ayon (Disagree)	Low
1.00-1.79	Lubos na hindi sumasang-ayon (Strongly Disagree)	Very Low

Ethical Considerations

After obtaining permission, the researchers discussed and presented informed consent to the participants. Essential components of the consent were the assurance of anonymity, the rights of the participants to withdraw and withhold their data, and the assurance of confidentiality. Because participants' important profiles were gathered, questionnaires were kept in a secure cabinet that only the researchers could access.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Extent of Psychosocial Well-being of Respondents*

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Description
1. Emotional Safety	4.13	Agree
2. Self-awareness	3.40	Agree
3. Self-expression	3.17	Neutral
4. Self-regulation	3.83	Agree
5. Problem-solving (help-seeking)	4.05	Agree
6. Problem-solving (self-reliant)	3.86	Agree
7. Self-confidence	3.38	Neutral
8. Empathy	4.21	Strongly Agree
Average	3.75	Agree

It can be gleaned in Table 2, the extent to which respondents manage the demands of daily life, cope with stressors and achieve their full potential. Notably, the respondents strongly agree that they understand what their classmates or neighbors are going through, or empathy (4.21). Meanwhile, respondents express neutrality in self-confidence (3.38) and self-expression (3.17). Overall, the average

rating of 3.75 indicates a general agreement among respondents regarding their psychosocial well-being.

Table 3. *Extent of Psychosocial Adjustment of Respondents to the Face-to-face Classes*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Description</i>
1. Affect	4.38	Strongly Agree
2. Motivation	4.32	Strongly Agree
3. Perception of face-to-face modality vis-à-vis academic learning	4.26	Strongly Agree
4. Perceived physical safety	4.46	Strongly Agree
5. Self-agency towards physical safety	3.99	Agree
Average	4.28	Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the extent of psychosocial adjustment of respondents to the return of face-to-face classes, indicating the overall attitude of learners towards this transition. The responses suggest a strong agreement among the respondents in areas, namely, perceived physical safety (4.46), affect (4.38), motivation (4.32), and perception of face-to-face learning in comparison to academic learning (4.26). The lowest mean among the dimensions is self-agency towards physical safety (3.99), translated as agree. The computed grand mean on the extent of psychosocial adjustment of respondents to the return of face-to-face classes is 4.28, translated to respondents' strongly agreement.

A school serves as a vital place where people can grow in their abilities, morals, and adaptability. Students' general psychosocial well-being and adjustments must be assessed and monitored as schools move from remote learning to in-person modality, as it remains a critical societal concern. Any institution's quality of education is primarily determined by how well teachers and students perform. In light of this, paying attention to the many variables influencing their well-being and adjustment in an ever-changing environment is critical.

Based on careful interpretation and data analysis, the rating of 3.75 suggests that learners have a "high" level of psychosocial well-being. This implies that participants can be positioned well for the challenges and opportunities of returning to face-to-face classes. For instance, students who exhibit high levels of psychosocial wellbeing are more likely to be better prepared to handle the possible concerns with in-person classes. As a result, when confronted with social interactions and academic challenges, these learners are inclined to remain calm, concentrate on their goals, and actively seek responsive assistance, enhancing their chances of success in the classroom. In addition, students with proficient interpersonal skills may experience greater ease in participating in group work or collaborative activities within the classroom environment, boosting their entire educational experience. However, there are areas, such as self-reflection and self-confidence, where learners may benefit from additional support and development to thrive fully in in-person classes. This result supports various findings which state that emotional safety, self-awareness, self-regulation, problem-solving skills, and empathy are critical components of psychosocial well-being (Kessler et al., 2020; Smith & Jones, 2019; Betz, 2022; Raising Children, 2021; Llego, 2022; Goleman, 2005). It indicates that learners encounter difficulties evaluating their abilities and weaknesses, which impede their ability to handle academic activities and obstacles effectively, and understanding better themselves as they establish a sense of inadequacy inside the educational environment.

Conversely, the psychosocial adjustment results indicating a "Very High" level imply that learners feel better and excited about the continuous return of face-to-face classes after the pandemic. As stated in the PSBE interpretation of learner ratings and recommendations, this entails providing an opportunity to integrate and continue helpful practices that learners could gain during distance learning and year one of face-to-face classes. Some strategies include but are not limited to encouraging students' motivation and positive attitudes, enhancing the perception of in-person instruction through dynamic and engaging classroom and school-wide activities, making sure sufficient physical safety precautions are taken, and equipping students with the information and abilities to take responsibility for their safety (Llego, 2022).

Conclusions

This quantitative, descriptive study assessed secondary learners' psychosocial well-being and adjustment as they transitioned to face-to-face classes. Notable findings revealed that learners perceived themselves to have moderate skills in expressing thoughts and feelings and showcasing their strengths and abilities in school. These insights underscore the importance of incorporating recommended activities from the 2022 Psychosocial Support Activity Pack by the Department of Education into a school-based psychosocial well-being program. These activities could include reflective exercises on managing complex emotions, relaxation techniques, and confidence-building exercises to foster holistic growth.

Furthermore, the implications of this study extend to the Guidance and Counseling Services of the institution, urging them to design responsive mental health awareness programs that focus on enhancing learners' self-expression and self-confidence.

The study recognizes its limitations despite these valuable findings. In order to provide a more in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, future studies may employ qualitative or mixed-method approaches. Furthermore, carrying out comparative case studies across multiple sites would improve generalizability and fortify the data proving correlations or causation; more importantly, the current

study utilized self-reported Likert items that may be deemed subjective. Finally, future researchers may consider looking at or creating culturally sensitive scales that accurately measure psychosocial well-being and adjustment within the Filipino setting to ensure a more thorough grasp of the variables being studied.

References

- Aristovnik, A., Keržič, D., Ravšelj, D., Tomaževič, N., & Umek, L. (2020). Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on life of higher education students: A global perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(20).
- Barowski, J. & Orr, S. (2021, November 19) "What is Self-Expression", Study.com <https://study.com/learn/lesson/self-expression-concept-examples.html#:~:text=The%20definition%20of%20self%2Dexpression,a%20form%20of%20self%2Dexpression>.
- Betz, M. (2022) "What is self-awareness and why is it important?" Better Up <https://www.betterup.com/blog/what-is-selfawareness#:~:text=Psychologists%20Shelley%20Duval%20and%20Robert,align%20with%20your%20internal%20standards>.
- Brenner, H. & Letich, L. (2023) Emotional Safety: What It Is and Why It's Important. *The Art of Feeling*. Psychology Today. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/the-art-of-feeling/202301/emotional-safety-what-it-is-and-why-its-important#:~:text=Emotional%20safety%20is%20the%20visceral,and%20more%20difficulty%20reaching%20out>.
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432.
- Green, S. P., Jackson, M. L., & Davis, A. R. (2021). The role of school-based counseling services in promoting psychosocial well-being among secondary school students. *School Psychology Review*, 50(1), 68-82.
- Harrison, L. R., & Adams, D. R. (2020). Mindfulness and stress reduction in secondary schools: A systematic review of the literature. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(4), 711-727.
- Kessler, S. M., Turner, J. R., & Baker, L. A. (2020). Family support and psychosocial well-being in secondary school students. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 34(2), 193-204.
- Kumar, C. (2020). Psychosocial well-being of individuals. *Quality Education*, 676-686.
- Larson, J. (1996). The World Health Organization's definition of health: Social versus spiritual health. *Soc. Indic. Res.* 38:181-192. doi: 10.1007/BF00300458
- Llego, M. A. (2022, August 20). DEPED Psychosocial Support Activity Pack for teachers. TeacherPH. https://www.teacherph.com/deped-psychosocial-support-activity-pack-teachers/#Psychosocial_Support_Activity_Pack_for_Teachers_Kinder_Grades_1-3_and_Senior_High_School
- Llego, M. A. (2022, August 21). DePED Psychosocial Support Evaluation Guide. TeacherPH. https://www.teacherph.com/deped-psychosocial-support-evaluation-guide/#Pagsusuri_sa_Sikososyal_Para_sa_Balik_Eskwela_Grades_11_to_12
- Loades, M. E., Chatburn, E., Higson-Sweeney, N., Reynolds, S., Shafran, R., Brigden, A., & Crawley, E. (2020). Rapid systematic review: The impact of social isolation and loneliness on the mental health of children and adolescents in the context of COVID-19. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 59(11), 1218-1239.
- Madariaga J. M., Arribillaga A., Zulaika L. M. (2014). Components and relationships of a structural model of psychosocial adjustment in adolescence. *International Journal of Developmental and Educational Psychology*, 6, 303-310.
- Martikainen, P. (2002). Psychosocial determinants of health in social epidemiology. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 31. doi: 10.1093/ije/31.6.1091.
- McCombes, S. (2023, June 22). Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Nsereko, N., David, N., Seggane, M., Janet, N. & Denis, S. (2014). Psychosocial problems and development of psychopathology among Ugandan university students. *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 3, 3-16.
- RaisingChildren.net.au (2021, May 20) "Self-regulation in children & teenagers: Understanding behaviour. <https://raisingchildren.net.au/toddlers/behaviour/understanding-behaviour/self-regulation#:~:text=with%20self%2Dregulation,What%20is%20self%2Dregulation%20frustration%20excitement%20anger%20and%20embarrassment>
- Smith, C. D., & Jones, E. F. (2019). Peer relationships and psychosocial well-being among secondary school students: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48(5), 950-963.
- Thomas, L. (2023, December 18). Simple Random Sampling | Definition, Steps & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/simple-random-sampling/>

Uludag, O. & Oney, E. (2013). Classification of self-confidence: Is general self-confidence an aggregate of specific self-confidences? In 6th International Conference on Service Management (pp. 20-22).

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

John Noel E. Fermin

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines

May Caroline C. Gajes

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines

Alyssa Dianne Paulette F. Guda

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines

Gracious Bai B. Cariaga

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines

Felisa R. Andres

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines

Dianne M. David

University of La Salette, Incorporated – Philippines